

COMPARATIVE VIDEO EDITING PROGRAMS

Senior Lecturer

Polvonov Kholbek Nematovich

*Department of optical communication systems and network security, counter
branch of Tashkent University of Information Technology named after*

Muhammad al-Khwarazmi

Tel.: +998 (99) 688-02-04.

E-mail: polvonovxolbek1234@gmail.com

The main tasks of video editing are: cutting out unnecessary video fragments, gluing together separate sections of video material, creating a transition between them, adding effects and inserting captions. There are three types of video editing: linear, non-linear and hybrid.

Key words: *video editing, montage, television, video, audio, linear editing.*

Linear editing is real-time editing. Data from several sources, for example, several cameras, comes through the switch to the receiver. Next, the director of linear editing switches the signal sources and displays what he needs on the screen. Also, linear editing is used to cut scenes without violating their sequence.

With nonlinear editing, the video is converted to digital form after it is divided into fragments, then these fragments are recorded in the sequence necessary for the user, in the required format, to the selected video medium. At the same time, not all of the source video material may fall into the final file; it may be partially trimmed.

Non-linear editing came into active use on television after the advent of computers that are capable of processing digital video in real time. Such installation is carried out using special computer programs called video editors. One of the important advantages of non-linear editing is the unnecessary of completely rewriting the final video file to work with it (changing the sequence, cutting or deleting unnecessary parts of the recording).

Hybrid editing combines the advantages of linear and non-linear editing (non-linear video editing system acts as a video source). The disadvantage is usually a higher price.

Recently, non-linear editing has virtually replaced other types of video editing from our lives.

Video editing software overview

Currently, there are a fairly large number of software tools for video editing. Each of them has different functionality and is designed for users with different levels of knowledge. Consider some of the most popular video editing software.

Рисунок 1. Adobe premiere screen.

Adobe Premiere Pro

This is just a great program with which the user can import and process a variety of video recordings, the ability to insert records of different quality and formats into one work, whether it's video from a phone or an HD-quality clip and even a movie in excess of the modern format, the program will still be able to process as you want, and at the end of the installation, transcoding is not required. A clear and accessible interface makes it easy for a novice user to work, and the number of functions provides many opportunities for a professional.

Рисунок 2. Pinnacle Studio screen.

Pinnacle Studio

With Pinnacle Studio you have the opportunity to view two imported videos in parallel and work with frames from any. The list of options includes functions such as stabilization and color correction, with which you can correct errors that occurred during recording. This is just a great program for professional video processing, but video editing enthusiasts should consider some other video editor.

***Рисунок 3. Edius Pro screen.
Edius***

Professional video editor that can work with video files in 4K, 3D and HD. One of the advantages of this program is its tremendous processing and rendering speed, thanks to which the data is processed almost in real time, without any delays. Another significant advantage of this program is an unlimited number of tracks. The program is actively used to create music videos, short films and television news releases. For novice users, this program will be difficult to learn.

***Рисунок 4. Movavi Video Editor screen.
Movavi Video Editor***

Movavi Video Editor is a multifunctional video editor that is able to work

with all popular multimedia formats. The functionality of this program has all the necessary set of tools for video processing, as well as an impressive range of effects and filters. In its simplicity, it is perfect for beginners of video editing. And in its functionality, it is not inferior to professional programs. however, the only minus of the program pushes it away from professional use - this is the number of tracks, it is one.

Рисунок 5. Sony Vegas Pro screen.

Sony Vegas Pro

SONY Vegas Pro is a representative of a family of professional video editors. It is used by television video monitors, web developers and those who produce short films. Initially, for novice users, the program interface will seem difficult to understand, but after a couple of hours of working with this program, you will notice that all the tools are exactly where they belong.

Рисунок 6. Studio Windows (Movie Marker) screen.

Studio Windows (Movie Maker)

Everyone knows that the Windows Film Studio is a useful and time-tested video editing program. The application is perfect for beginners and is an intuitive editor for home use. This program allows you to receive video from various sources, process it using various transitions and effects, create titles,

<https://tiame66.uz>

<https://uz-conference.com>

titles, cut and glue fragments. In general, the program consists of a content area, a pasteboard and a preview window. The program also has a quick access panel in which you can pin your frequently used commands. The disadvantages of the program include the fact that it has a small set of tools for working with video and saving it only in a single format — wmv. Therefore, for professionals this program is unlikely to work.

We will collect all the advantages and disadvantages of video editing software systems described above in the final table (table 1), which will clearly show us the result of the comparative analysis according to 6 criteria: number of tracks, level of effects, the ability to capture video, video resolution, paid or free access and formats are not supported by this program.

Table 1.

Comparative review of video editing software

The name of the program	Unsupported formats	Timeline tracks	Effects	Effects	Resolution	Spread
Adobe Premiere Pro	-	∞	super	+	4K	Trial
Pinnacle Studio	RM, QT	12	normal	-	1080p	Trial
Edius	-	∞	super	+	4K	Trial
Movavi Video Editor	QT, RM, FLV	1	normal	-	1080p	Trial
Sony Vegas Pro	-	∞	super	+	4K	Trial
Studio Windows (Movie Maker)	QT, RM, FLV	1	few	+	720p	Free

Video Editing Web Resources

In addition to software systems, video editing can also be done using various web resources. The most famous of them will be considered below.

**Рисунок 7. Studio Windows (Movie Marker) screen.
 Youtube editor**

YouTube Video Editor allows the user to edit video recordings from his profile directly in the browser. With its help, you can carry out tricky manipulations such as cutting, gluing transitions and text inserts. All this happens based on user uploaded video.

**Рисунок 8. PopcornMaker screen.
PopcornMaker**

PopcornMaker- It is an online editor with all the classic features. When you get to the service's website, you see an editing "table" where you can immediately start your work (cutting, gluing, transitions, text comments).

**Рисунок 9. FileLab Video Editor screen.
FileLab Video Editor**

The FileLab Video Editor, like the previous analogues, offers the user a standard set of functions. With it, you can process your video recordings by adding transitions and effects.

CONCLUSION

Video editing is the removal of unnecessary sections of the video and the reduction of the video sequence into one whole. But we do not just delete

unnecessary parts, we compose the video in such a way that it looks as a whole, and the film does not lose its meaning. For this they use video editors. Currently, there are a huge number of them that are perfect for professionally processing video information, as well as for home video processing, to carry out classical manipulations with video files it's not even necessary to install any software, everything can be done online in a browser.

LITERATURE

1. Abramova O. F. Ispolzovaniye multimediynix texnologiy v protsesse obucheniya dissipline «Kompyuternaya grafika»// O. F. Abramova, S. V. Belova// Jurnal «Uspexi sovremennogo yestestvoznaniya» №3, 2012 god, str. 90-91.
2. Arbuzov V.P. Ispolzovaniye texnologii Landing Page pri proyektirovanii sovremennogo sayta [Elektronniy resurs] / V.P. Arbuzov, O.F. Abramova // Sovremenniye nauchniye issledovaniya i innovatsii. - 2015. - № 1. - C. Rejim dostupa: <http://web.snauka.ru/issues/2015/01/43465>.
3. Elektronniy resurs <http://softobase.com/>
4. Elektronniy resurs <http://videomount.blogspot.ru/>
5. Borodavchenko D.V. Svetovoye resheniye interfeysa kak sredstvo povisheniya effektivnosti raboti IS [Elektronniy resurs] / D.V. Borodavchenko, O.F. Abramova // Studencheskiy nauchniy forum – 2015: dokl. VII mejdunar. stud. elektron. nauch. konf. Napravleniye «Texnicheskiye nauki» (Seksiya «Aktualniye problemi kompyuternoy vizualizatsii») / RAYE. - Moskva, 2015. - C. 1-9. – Rejim dostupa: <http://www.scienceforum.ru/2015/pdf/12143.pdf>.
7. Voljanov A.A. Graficheskiy interfeys kak sredstvo vizualizatsii obsheniya A.A. Voljanov, O.F. Abramova // Studencheskiy nauchniy forum 2014: dokl. VI mejdunar. stud. elektron. nauch. konf., 15 fevr. – 31 marta 2014 g. Napravl.: Texnicheskiye nauki / RAYE. - M., 2014. - C. 1-4. –Rejim dostupa: <http://www.scienceforum.ru/2014/pdf/6827.pdf>.
8. Zubexin A.A. Sovremenniy web-sayt: modniye tendensii v komponovke i svete [Elektronniy resurs] / A.A. Zubexin, O.F. Abramova // Studencheskiy nauchniy forum – 2015: dokl. VII mejdunar. stud. elektron. nauch. konf. Napravleniye «Texnicheskiye nauki» (Seksiya «Aktualniye problemi kompyuternoy vizualizatsii») / RAYE. - Moskva, 2015.: <http://www.scienceforum.ru/2015/pdf/11238.pdf>.
9. Ochilovich, S. Z., Abduganievich, D. N., Nematovich, S. S., & Sadirovich, S. N. (2021). EFFECT OF FORCES ON AIR CONVEYING DEVICES AND NETWORK ON COTTON SEED QUALITY. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(12), 771-775.
10. Nematovich, S. S., Abduganievich, D. N., & Sadirovich, S. N. (2021). TECHNOLOGY OF PRODUCTION OF CERAMIC MATERIALS AND ITS VALUE TODAY. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(12), 768-770.
11. Ochilovich, S. Z., Abdug'aniyevich, D. N., Ne'matovich, S. S., & Sadirovich, S. N. M. (2021). Methods Of Kinematic Study of Flat Base Mechanisms. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 3, 208-214.
12. Садир Нематович Шодиев1, Неъматжон Садирович Шодиев2. (2024). ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ВЛИЯНИЯ ЗАБИВАЕМОСТИ ТРУБОК РАДИАТОРА НА ТЕПЛОВОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ ДВИГАТЕЛЯ. *Uz-Conferences*, 1(1), 145–151. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/32>
13. Usarov, Jabbor E; Eshnaev, Nortoji J; Khakimov, Jamshid O; Saidova, Dilobar I; Ikrom Sh Inoyatov; и другие. *NeuroQuantology*; Bornova Izmir Том 20, Изд. 16, (2022): 4614 - 4622. DOI:10.48047/NQ.2022.20.16.NQ880468 <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/social-significance-creating-mechanism/docview/2816741596/se-2>
14. Shodiev, Z. O., Inoyatov, I. S., & Shodiev, N. S. (2020). NATURAL PASTE AND ITS

- VALUE TODAY. In Эффективность применения инновационных технологий и техники в сельском и водном хозяйстве (pp. 198-200).
15. J.Sh.Fazliev., Sh.M.Tojiev., Sh.D.Khalikov. (2024). EFFICIENCY OF USE OF CLAY WATER WITH DROP IRRIGATION. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 504–509. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/107>
16. I.J.Xudayev, I.J.Xudayev, & Sh.M.Tojiyev. (2024). NAMLATGICH-BLOKLARDAN HOSIL QILINGAN EKTRANLI EGATLARDAN G'O'ZANI SUG'ORISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 514–519. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/109>
17. Fazliyev, Z. S., Shokhimardonova, N. S., Sobirov, F. T., Ravshanov, U. K., & Baratov, S. S. (2014). Technology of the drip irrigation use in gardens and vineyards. The Way of Science, 56.
18. Shodiyev Ne'matjon. (2024). INTEGRATIV YONDASHUV ASOSIDA UMUMKASBIY FANLARNI O'QITISHNING ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALARI. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 945–950. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/195>
19. Shodiyev Ne'matjon. (2024). TEXNIKA OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA UMUMKASBIY FANLARNI AXBOROT TA'LIM MUHITIDA O'QITISHNING MUHIM YO'NALISHLARI. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 938–944. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/194>
20. Fazliyev, J. (2017). Drip irrigation technology in gardens. Интернаука. Science Journal, 7(11).
21. Фазлиев, Ж.Ш.(2017).Боғларда томчилатиб суғориш технологияси. Интернаука,(7-3),71-73.
22. Ikrom, I. (2023). KASBIY TAYYORGARLIKNING RIVOJLANISH DINAMIKASI BO'YICHA PEDAGOGIK TAJRIBA-SINOV ISHLARI NATIJALARINING TAHLILI. In Uz-Conferences (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 626-633).
23. Shaxrilloevich, I. I. (2023). DIDACTIC CONDITIONS FOR THE PREPARATION OF STUDENTS OF VOCATIONAL EDUCATION FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY BASED ON AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH. Academia Repository, 4(10), 142-145.
24. Саримсаков, М. М. (2023, May). СПОСОБЫ ПОЛИВА И УРОЖАЙНОСТЬ ИНТЕНСИВНЫХ ЯБЛОНЕВЫХ САДОВ. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE (Vol. 2, No. 14, pp. 173-175).
25. Фазлиев, Ж. Ш., & Шохимарданова, Н. Ш. (2024). БОҒЛАРНИ ТОМЧИЛАТИБ СУҒОРИШДА ТУПРОҚ-ГРУНТ НАМЛАНИШ КОНТУРИНИ АНИҚЛАШ УСЛУБИ. IMRAS, 7(2), 34-38.
26. Sadirovich, S. N. (2022). The Significance of Problem Situation Assignments in Teaching the Science of Machine Details. Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science, 3(8), 30-32.
27. Shodiev, N. S. (2022). USE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN PREPARING ENGINEERING STUDENTS FOR PROJECT-CONSTRUCTION ACTIVITY. Экономика и социум, (10-2 (101)), 167-169.
28. AZ, S. Z. S. N. S. (2020). Analysis of the work on improving the design of dryers inside the ginning plants and the mode of drying.
29. Shodiyev Ziyodullo Ochilovich, & Shodiyev Nematjon Sadirovich. (2022). KINEMATIC STUDY OF FLAT BASE MECHANISMS. E Conference Zone, 61–69. Retrieved from <https://www.econferencezone.org/index.php/ecz/article/view/888>
30. Ochilovich, S. Z. (2020, September). Inoyatov Ikrom Shaxriloyevich, Shodiyev Ne'matjon Sadirovich. Tabiiy yaylovlar va uning bugungi kundagi ahamiyati. In Эффективность применение инновационных технологий и техники в сельском и водном хозяйстве» международная научно-практическая онлайн-конференция (pp. 25-

26).

31. Shodiyev, Z. O., & Shodiyev, N. S. (2020). TO STUDY THE EFFECT OF THE MESH SURFACE ON THE SEED COTTON DURING THE SEPARATION OF COTTON FROM THE AIR STREAM. In Эффективность применения инновационных технологий и техники в сельском и водном хозяйстве (pp. 121-122).

32. Shodiyev, Z. O., & Shodiyev, N. S. (2020). KEY FACTORS FOR INCLUSION IN THE EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN IN THE CXM SEPARATOR AND THEIR IDENTIFICATION. In Эффективность применения инновационных технологий и техники в сельском и водном хозяйстве (pp. 119-121).

33. Musinovich, S. M. (2023, June). DRIP IRRIGATION INTENSIVE APPLE ORCHARDS AND SEASONAL WATER CONSUMPTION. In Proceedings of Scientific Conference on Multidisciplinary Studies (Vol. 2, No. 6, pp. 8-14).

34. Khamidov, M. K., Juraev, U. A., Buriev, X. B., Juraev, A. K., Saksonov, U. S., Sharifov, F. K., & Isabaev, K. T. (2023, February). Efficiency of drip irrigation technology of cotton in saline soils of Bukhara oasis. In IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science (Vol. 1138, No. 1, p. 012007). IOP Publishing.

35. Sharifov Firdavs, & Mirzamurotov Mirshod. (2024). G'O'ZA O'SIMLIGINI YETISHTIRISHDA SUV TEJAMKOR SUG'ORISH TEXNOLOGIYALARINI QO'LLASH. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 461–464. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/98>

36. Sattorovich, S. U., & Qobil o'g'li, S. F. (2022). BUG 'DOY O 'SIMLIGI VA DONINING XALQ XO 'JALIGIDA BUGUNGI KUNDAGI AHAMIYATI.

37. Xamrayev Kamol, Sharifov Firdavs, & Yusupova Oynura. (2024). TUPROQ SHO'RINI YUVISHDA BIOSOLVENT BIRIKMASINI TUPROQ SUV-TUZ MUVOZANATIGA TA'SIRI. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 458–460. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/97>

38. Фазлиев, Ж., Тожиев, Ш., & Холиков, Ш. (2023). СПОСОБЫ ЭКОНОМИИ ВОДНЫХ РЕСУРСОВ В САДАХ. In Uz-Conferences (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 520-525).

39. Xudayev, I. J., & Tojiyev, S. M. (2023). NAMLATGICH-BLOKLARDAN HOSIL QILINGAN EKTRANLI EGATLARDAN G 'O 'ZANI SUG 'ORISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. In Uz-Conferences (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 514-519).

40. Fazliev, J. S., Tojiev, S. M., & Khalikov, S. D. (2023). EFFICIENCY OF USE OF CLAY WATER WITH DROP IRRIGATION. In Uz-Conferences (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 504-509).

41. Fazliyev, J. (2017). Drip irrigation technology in gardens. Интернаука. Science Journal, 7(11).

42. Фазлиев, Ж. Ш. (2019). EFFICIENCY OF USE OF CLAY WATER WITH DROP IRRIGATION. ЖУРНАЛ АГРО ПРОЦЕССИНГ, (4).

43. Худайев, И., & Фазлиев, Ж. ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ КАПЕЛЬНОГО ОРОШЕНИЯ САДОВ И ВИНОГРАДНИКОВ. JURNALI, 176

44. Fazliyev, J. (2018). Modern irrigation methods for gardens. Science, 22, 24-26.

45. Худайев, И., Фазлиев, Ж., & Шаропов, Н. (2019). Капельное орошения-как водосберегающий способ орошения садов и виноградников. Школа Науки, (4), 17-18.

46. Ismoil, K., Jamoliddin, F., & Giyos, H. (2020). Water supply equipment and technology for irrigation in difficult conditions of desert-steppe zones. Journal of critical reviews, 7(11), 3102-3106.

47. Худайев, И. Ж., Фазлиев, Ж., & Хамзаев, Г. (2020). ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ВОДОБЕСПЕЧЕННОСТИ ЗЕМЕЛЬ ЗА СЧЕТ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ КОЛЛЕКТОРНО-ДРЕНАЖНЫХ ВОД. Universum: технические науки, (11-3 (80)), 5-7.

48. Фазлиев, Ж. Ш., & Баратов, С. С. (2014). ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ГЛИНИСТОЙ ВОДЫ ПРИ КАПЕЛЬНОМ ОРОШЕНИИ. The Way of Science, (4), 77.